

ChatGPT and Imaginative Reasoning in the Classroom Space: What would be your design for a campaign to persuade people to adopt a plant-based diet?

Unthinkable Ideas, Data

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Abstract / Introduction

What would be your design for a campaign to persuade people to adopt a plant-based diet? ... is the question presented to a small group (20) of students in a *Prevention Research* science class. The question is presented post the class members' analysis of the paper <http://bit.ly/Ornishetal2013>. The presentation is accompanied by the argument that the food we eat can introduce risks and uncertainties. And the *EU's Precautionary Principle* calls for preventive action in the face of uncertain but suggestive evidence of danger. Our food sources are proposed as subjects for scrutiny as a danger to Public Health and the biodiversity on Earth. We are not doing Fossil Fuels

here, but it is undoubtedly super high on uncertain but suggestive evidence of danger to Public Health and the biodiversity on Earth.

This paper is a living document, an active document that is proposed to travel through versions corresponding to the passing of each semester.

The title I am working with is *Language Models and Imaginative Reasoning in the Classroom Space* and you are welcome to make suggestions on every aspect of this document. We are in the era of #openai> #ChatGPT and Google> #Bard; I opted for Bard because there was not a paywall for me nor the Classroom Space, 20230919.

The Url for the live page hosting this document is <https://bit.ly/PlantBasedDietCampaign>

Keywords

- Ultra-Processed_Foods, PrecautionaryPrinciple, Plant-Based Diet, LanguageModels, ChatGPT, Bard, LearningSpace, HealthDisparities, HealthGradients, ImaginativeReasoning, RootCauses,

Materials & Methods, Results, Conclusions

This paper is a work in progress, it is also a proposal of how to develop a learning space with Language Models: *OpenAI> ChatGPT* and *Google> Bard*. I do not as yet have the *Results* and *Conclusions* from that classroom space; we are currently in the first semester of its operation. Here I present the *Materials & Methods* and *initial results*,

Work In Progress

My work is in progress on designing the initial *Assignment*¹ in my course, *Prevention Research*.² The current focus is on the *fourth part* of the Assignment; the progress of the course is mapped in the form of announcements named 'Note_'. The fourth part was initially

¹ Questions for an #IdeasLab Learning Space: https://bit.ly/Assignment_1_

² Prevention Research ... My course description,

referenced in Note_4³ on Assignment_1. Feel free to make suggestions, all are welcome ... this document is intended to be a collaborative testing out of a question for an *#IdeasLab Learning Space* and https://bit.ly/Assignment_1_.

- The question for the fourth part of https://bit.ly/Assignment_1_, developing our *#IdeasLab* approach is: **What would be your design for a campaign to persuade people to adopt a plant-based diet?** ... This campaign is relevant after we analyze the <http://bit.ly/Ornishetal2013> results.
 - I hope you have come across the (Large) Language Model, ChatGPT, by openai (<- Google It) ... I pitch it as an ally, a thing to use and learn about, and a peek into the future. I used ChatGPT with the above question. The results suggested to me that I redefine the question, to add more precise significance. I am considering geospatial science, epidemiology, and environmental health science; my question now has **locality**,⁴ I am working on giving it **positionality** after Kovach (2009)⁵
 - ... I will place the question/request just North of East 96th, https://bit.ly/Borders_96th, and ask for **"imaginative reasoning"**⁶ and attention to evidence; concerning these it is **positionality** that will likely be a must have co-traveler. I would ask you to let your thoughts be open to **positionality** on such questions. Please consider the role of **positionality** for reasoning, causal reasoning: https://www.evernote.com/l/AAd625eP1xBCT7Iw1IQcI_Z_weDttUQzK3JY. I am not going South of East 96th Street with this request because there are staggering socioeconomic transitions that according to <http://bitly.com/ChettyEtAl2016> play a significant role in health, one of the authors in the Chetty et al study said, - I(KM) am paraphrasing - it is something like the richest Americans winning the war on Cancer. Rojas et al. (2023)

³ Note_4, 2023012251710UTC

⁴ Just North of East 96th, https://bit.ly/Borders_96th,

⁵ Margaret Kovach (2009) *Indigenous Methodologies: Characteristics, Conversations, and Contexts*. Again published 2021: https://www.google.com/books/edition/Indigenous_Methodologies/jI9DEAAAQBAJ?hl=en brought forward a skepticism from me(KM), we need to ask about methods, who, what is being measured, who is the measurer, who is measuring the measurer, and what is the role of my / your **positionality** on choices I/you make on all of this.

⁶ Progress on a description for **"imaginative reasoning"** -> I am pitching a *scientific imagination as needed for that notion on an underlying biological mechanism(s) for our exposure-outcome theory*. I am pitching a *scientific imagination* as skeptical, statistical thinking (Tong (2019)) and causal thinking using a totality of the circumstances: you (**positionality**) have gathered on the exposures, outcomes, **localities**, **positionalities**. This is a prompt to be conscious of who is measuring the measurer as you measure. *We are trying to develop Imaginative Reasoning*

#MyNotes from thinking about Kovach (2009) on **positionality**

- Asking others to tell the story of what they are eating and advising them on increasing plant-based food consumption requires *Storyboard* planning: **(A)** In the operation of a “story-based methodology,” the researcher’s disclosure of self (see Kovach on “self-location” in Chapter 5 ‘Story as Indigenous Methodology’, page 98: *“In asking others to share their stories, it is necessary to share our own, starting with self-location.”*) is of critical value because it provides interlocutors (+ readers, listeners) with very good, best estimate guessing games to my /our /their motivations. **(B)** Pitching disclosure on the subject matter provides the same value. **(C)** Disclosures can also make (troubling/reassuring) inconsistencies more visible. **(D)** A “self-location”/identification becomes a consideration because telling stories involves curating stories and citation sources in ways that move focuses either intentionally or unintentionally, ... Dears, see this way forward “shift the focus away from structurally defined axes of oppression” (Fernandes (2017): Chapter 1, ‘Curated Storytelling’, page 3 of 15. The full sentence is: ‘Curated personal stories shift the focus away from structurally defined axes of oppression and help to defuse the confrontational politics of social movements.’ In circumstances needing change without delay, the confrontation part might prove very useful.) Some of us are conducting research on sites that are touched with a colonial remainder of differing hues ... disclosures instigated by Kovach become of vital significance. **(E)** Disclosing intersectional **positionalities** of the tellers of the stories, including commitments to and investments in making the story speak to others’ needs and desires is a must for journeying without a pre-existing script. Reading, researching, investigating, writing, speaking, ... can become avenues for **futurism**.
- Think about it, my (KM) sense and conversations shared with me show a disengagement from Science within communities under stress. Stress can range from Racism to Pollution, see <https://bit.ly/TheCircumstances>. Bridging gaps in knowledge, support and education to empower these communities is vital work. This is what we bring, this what we nurture in

our workshops and this is what we promote for peer-to-peer mentoring⁷

⁷ **Whose Futurism?** Bringing in Plant-Based Diets are likely steps toward Public Health and Environmental Health protections. One of the objectives for an #IdeasLab approach is **Futurism**: speculatively writing on precautionary strategies, reducing the harms at the root causes of Health Disparities.

Upshot Reflections on using ChatGPT post the drafting of this Paper

- Reflections on using ChatGPT: it appears it can't theorize/hypothesize yet.⁸ I would therefore plan on distinguishing your work from a ChatGPT result by hypothesizing, and theorizing on the issues presented ... please review the ChatGPT output on an issue and distinguish your thinking from a ChatGPT output or credit that ChatGPT output. My take is that AI> (Large) Language Model> ChatGPT⁹ cannot do the best estimate using a totality of the circumstances approach at a (**locality**) and with the **positionality**: you, me, we, our study brings to the site. Kovach (2009)
 - I checked out the status of discussions on Reddit - a very limited check by me, I went to [r/MachineLearning](#) ... The conversations are changing rapidly, at 20230131084106NYC I liked the reporting of @mkzoucha who argues that the language models (LMs)> ChatGPT will be constantly newer with more parameters and better text generation so detection of ChatGPT work-product is likely wasting my/your time. I liked the messaging identifying attempts to humanize ChatGPT output by asking for "perplexity" with an identified score of over 9000. See my attempt below.

Health Disparity Gradients and Borders

- **Back To The Assignment**: I would like you to consider the Health Disparity Gradients and Borders at this East 96th Street intersection and design an intervention to motivate and guide people in this locale to adopt a Plant-based Diet, **we can also think about can diet choices mitigate detrimental health encounters**.^{10 11}
- The **locality** I want you to focus on has a high incidence of Child Asthma Hospitalizations. I thought the streets were hotspots for air pollutants; I cycled to work through the **locality**, and the transitions in air quality is noticeable. Making this **locality** the focus was driven by a coincidence of the

⁸ "Imaginative Reasoning" is derived from "imaginative reason" as used in "The School of Giorgione" by Walter Pater, No. XXII n.s. (1877) of The Fortnightly Review. <https://fortnightlyreview.co.uk/2020/10/school-giorgione/> For the excerpt see <https://www.evernote.com/1/AAfHQiHZWoBAXKBPQOdwl3LfbT8w1cdllnw>. Pater (2020) I(KM) am proposing that we adopt "imaginative reasoning" for our analysis of a totality of the circumstances at https://bit.ly/Borders_96th.

⁹ In this review we used GPT3; GPT4 is already here.

¹⁰ Zhu et al. (2022)

¹¹ **What's going on?** E.g., Why these gradients and borders? Why are these gradients and borders reproducible across different disease states? **How do we go about identifying and investigating the root causes of these Health Disparities?** One of the guides to my investigatory approach is the **EU Precautionary Principle (PP)**. Commission (2000) A guiding text is provided by Martuzzi and Tickner (2004) for the investigatory steps towards the safety and protection of **communities and localities**. Contributors Stirling and Tickner write: '[] evidence of risk and uncertainty is examined to determine the possibility (and plausibility) of a significant health threat and the need for precautionary action.' See this excerpt <https://bit.ly/PrecautionaryAssessment>.

Figure 1: Health Borders

Asthma gradients and borders with the COVID-19 Disease Death gradients and borders. **What's going on?**¹² There is undoubtedly a range of modifiable and non-modifiable risk factors; these considerations appear later in the course. See Moses (2020) *Here I am just asking you about the above campaign in an identified locality, we are in the midst of the transitions crossing the East 96th Street intersection, at Second Avenue, Thinking North.*¹³ And there are Children, lots of Children,

"Save The Children"

- We will be considering just as different foods can have differing impacts on human health, they have different impacts on the environment, and the health of fauna, and flora. We can think about human health, the environment, clean air, food sources, and climate protection as interlinked. We can think about the biological, social, cultural, and political impacts of promoting a plant-based diet. Will promoting a plant-based diet led us to greater care and self-care as a collective? Will promoting a plant-based diet, lowering meat and processed meat consumption, lead us to more awareness of lowering methane production from Cattle, and lowering to zero #GreenHouseGases, #AirPollution?¹⁴ The primary goal of all of this is "Save The Children". The trajectory of obesity from childhood into

¹² See an excerpt from the 1973 film, "Save The Children" where Marvin Gaye makes this question the center, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Y9KC7uhMY9s>

¹³ For a totality of the circumstances at https://bit.ly/Borders_96th, please consider: Air Pollution, Other Pollutions, Food Desert, Stress of All Sorts, Racism, Other Aggressions, SocioEconomic Stress, Exercise, Trees on the Streets ... I often try the analysis: how many lives would be saved by cleaning the air?

¹⁴ Will promoting a plant-based diet steer us to greater care and self-care as a collective? Will promoting a plant-based diet steer us to promoting awareness and action on reducing pollution?

adulthood and accompanying disease states has to be one of our focus points.

**OBESE CHILDREN
ARE MORE LIKELY TO BE
OBESE ADULTS.**

SOURCE: CENTERS FOR DISEASE CONTROL AND PREVENTION

Figure 2: Save The Children

- **How do we avoid processed foods;** I argue an avoidance strategy is also a pathway to have people's eating desires be the driver of what the food industry provides, rather than the food industry telling us what we want. The development of avoidance strategies needs to be sustainable, motive is needed to continue avoidance; avoiding danger is a value that can be a motive. Educating the children on the dangers of **Ultra-Processed Foods** is proposed as a method of engaging moti-

vation for the development of avoidance strategies. Educating the children on the *Precautionary Principle* is proposed as a method for raising engagement with risk reduction and protection of people's health and environment health.

Communal, Community

- If we are going for a public-wide campaign a factor to be aware of is **No Universal Healthcare, USA (UHC, USA)**. Johnson (2021)¹⁵ I have not explored communal feelings toward individual health, Public Health, Environmental Health, and Health Messaging for this paper. Future projects in the course will cover these critical issues of forming **community**. This will include investigating the tools for detecting the role of racism in health.¹⁶
- On that word 'community', will it take a village to get some folks to adopt a plant-based diet, will it take individual marketing, how do we customize the approach for the nature of the communities?
 - We propose that a core tenet within the marketing strategy is proposing '**protection of children, people, and communities**', propose a policy that generates protective **code** standards,
 - The generation of protective **code** standards requires a policy position. This paper proposes the **Precautionary Principle** as that policy.
 - Protective **code** standards have to be strong enough such that the **code and enforcement** ensures that polluters do not injure or kill us with pollution. The **code** has to also provide us with a **margin of error** for those edge situations where the code fails and the polluter is egregious; we pitch this as the desired outcome: the people stay alive and uninjured,
- In response to increasing knowledge of **communities** and **climate** impacted by Air Pollution, and the role of Environmental

¹⁵ An investigation of **No Universal Healthcare, USA** impacts on **communal** healthcare, awareness of, caring for the health of your neighbor is relevant. Data gathering on instigating a situation of caring for the health of your neighbor as a public good to move towards is an included investigation in our research. There is this: "Childbirth Is Deadlier for Black Families Even When They're Rich, Expansive Study Finds." N.Y. Times, 15 Feb. 2023, <https://www.nytimes.com/interactive/2023/02/12/upshot/child-maternal-mortality-rich-poor.html>. Health disparities exist in apparent UHCs, the UK is an example: from '2016 onwards MBRRACE-UK has released reports on maternal morbidity rates, that show racial health disparities. The 2020 report 'Enquiries into Maternal Deaths and Morbidity' revealed that Black women are statistically four times more likely to die during childbirth than white women in the UK.' *Identifying the role of racism as a cause does not fit the timeframe available to this course but speculating does fit the timeframe of the course.*

¹⁶ Hardeman et al. (2022) "Developing Tools to Report Racism in Maternal Health for the CDC Maternal Mortality Review Information Application (MMRIA): Findings from the MMRIA Racism & Discrimination Working Group." *Matern. Child Health J.*, vol. 26, no. 4, 1, pp. 661 - 9. doi:10.1007/s10995-021-03284-3.

Health Science as an investigatory platform, we trademarked 'Climate Protection Fund',¹⁷ registered the NYS not-for-profit corporation 'Climate Protection Fund inc.', and registered the domains: ClimateProtectionFund.world, ClimateProtectionFund.eu and EnvironmentalJusticeMatters.org¹⁸ ... these are works in progress, content is in progress for these locations, we don't have anything up yet.

¹⁷ *Climate Protection Fund*

¹⁸ The direction of our work is here: <https://bit.ly/EnvironmentalJusticeMatters>

- The latest diet paper citing back to <http://bit.ly/Ornisheta12013> and presented as relevant to the *Course Members* work on **community** and diet is 'Building Health Equity: Action Steps From the American College of Lifestyle Medicine's Health Disparities Solutions Summit (HDSS) 2020.' Cassoobhoy et al. (2021) I put forward this excerpt as relevant to the work the course is engaging: 'With the Standard American Diet being comprised of an estimated 56% processed foods, 33% animal products, and 11% plant foods (upwards of 50% of these plant foods consisting of less healthy choices like French fries and fruit preserves), (Ref. 17) it is to be expected that a significant percentage of the population, magnified in our underserved **communities**, is overfed, (Ref. 18) fiber-deficient and nutrient-starved (Ref. 18 - 20) - leading to a pandemic of chronic disease.'
 - On that word 'community', the level of consumption of processed foods suggests we have to accommodate scale in our designs. Can the design be both micro-community-focused and on a national scale?

Here is my initial ChatGPT result:

Here is a potential design for a campaign to move people to a plant-based diet:

1. Develop a clear message: Develop a clear and compelling message that communicates the benefits of a plant-based diet, such as its potential to improve health, reduce environmental impact, and support animal welfare.
2. Use social media: Utilize social media platforms to reach a wide audience. Create engaging content that promotes plant-

based eating and shares success stories of people who have switched to a plant-based diet.

3. Partner with influencers: Partner with influencers in the health, wellness, and environmental communities to spread the message and reach new audiences.
4. Create a community: Build a community of plant-based eaters that can support and inspire one another. This can be done through social media groups, in-person meetups, or online forums.
5. Offer resources: Provide resources such as recipes, meal plans, and tips for making the transition to a plant-based diet.
6. Host events: Host events such as cooking classes, taste tests, and panel discussions to help people learn more about plant-based eating and connect with others who are interested in the topic.
7. Address concerns and misconceptions: Address concerns and misconceptions about plant-based diets, and provide accurate information to help people make informed decisions.

I(KM) provided Feedback to ChatGPT: I liked your listing because it covered both a micro and macro approach, ...

I then used "Regenerate" ChatGPT: ... By the way, I ran Grammarly on this page to tighten up the language,

Several key elements could be included in a campaign to encourage people to adopt a plant-based diet. Some possible strategies include:

1. Education: Provide clear and accurate information about the health benefits of plant-based diets, as well as the environmental and ethical reasons for reducing the consumption of animal products.
2. Accessibility: Make plant-based options readily available and affordable in a variety of settings, including grocery stores, restaurants, and schools.
3. Marketing: Use appealing and positive messaging to promote plant-based foods and dispel common misconceptions about them.

4. Community-building: Create and support a community of people who are interested in plant-based diets and provide opportunities for them to connect and support each other.
5. Celebrity endorsements: Using celebrities or influencers who promote plant-based diets.
6. Making it tasty: Highlighting the deliciousness of plant-based food and providing recipe ideas and cooking tips.

It would be important to tailor the campaign to the specific audience, taking into account cultural and socio-economic factors that may influence their food choices.

**I then did a redo with a declaration for a Perplexity of 6000, like so:
What would be your design for a campaign to move people to a plant-based diet? Perplexity 6000 ... here is the result:**

As a language model, I am trained to generate coherent and informative responses at various perplexity levels. However, a high perplexity setting of 6000 would likely result in a less concise and more detailed response, while still maintaining coherence.

A campaign to encourage people to adopt a plant-based diet could involve the following components:

1. Education: Provide comprehensive information on the health benefits of a plant-based diet, such as the lower risk of chronic diseases and improved heart health, as well as its positive impact on the environment, including reducing greenhouse gas emissions and preserving natural resources.
2. Accessibility: Ensure that plant-based food options are widely available, both in grocery stores and in restaurants. Consider offering cooking classes, workshops, and other resources to help people prepare plant-based meals.
3. Social Support: Create a supportive community around plant-based diets through social media, meet-ups, and other online forums. Encourage people to share their experiences, recipes, and tips.

4. Marketing: Utilize appealing and positive messaging to promote plant-based diets, emphasizing the delicious taste and variety of plant-based foods. Utilize influencers and celebrities who follow a plant-based diet to reach a wider audience.
5. Personalization: Cater the campaign to different audiences, taking into account cultural and socioeconomic factors that may influence their food choices. For example, targeting college students with messages about the environmental benefits of plant-based diets, or targeting families with messages about the health benefits for children.
6. Collaboration: Work with schools, employers, and other organizations to provide plant-based food options and support for those who are interested in adopting a plant-based diet.
7. Debunking Myths: Address common misconceptions about plant-based diets, such as the notion that they are lacking in essential nutrients or that they are more expensive than diets that include animal products.

Overall, a comprehensive and well-designed campaign could effectively encourage people to adopt a plant-based diet and support them in maintaining this lifestyle change.

Does ChatGPT sound, and feel Human,

Does it sound, feel more human to you, less machine-like with Perplexity? To me this sounded machine: “Cater the campaign to different audiences, taking into account cultural and socioeconomic factors that may influence their food choices.” Try reading it aloud, does it sound machine or human, and that choice of the word: “Cater” does it feel synthetic or human? Plus in the Assignment_1d that I am designing, your response would have to be **locality**-specific and **positionality** specific to the communities.

If you are thinking about the many reasons why am I directing you to this question, the front runner for me is I am arguing we have an emergency for the consumption of ultra-processed foods, and here is my argument:¹⁹

Ultra-processed foods are processed foods that are more modified, moved further away from their occurring in nature state by the addition of preservatives and artificial ingredients such as stabilizers and sweeteners. The additives can include added sugars: fructoses are often used, salts, and saturated fats / fatty acids; the actual nutritional value of these types of additives is either low or non-existent. A common stabilizer is xanthan gum which provides insights to the Gut Microbiome as a bacterial Eden that can become dysfunctional by exposing it to what is on the end of your fork. Ostrowski et al. (2022) Sulphur-related additives are routinely used as preservatives in processed meat; in the nutrition field, there are identifications of a Sulphur presence changing the demographics of the Gut Microbiome. 'Hydrogen sulfide (H₂S) is generated in the gut either by sulfur-reducing bacteria from inorganic sulfur (sulfate and sulfite) that is routinely used as a preservative in processed meat or by fermentative bacteria that metabolize organic sulfur compounds that are enriched in animal products such as red meat. (Ref. 3) Higher intakes of sulfur and sulfate were associated with an increased risk of Intestinal Bowel Syndrome, (Ref. 163) and fecal samples from patients with colon cancer have higher concentrations of H₂S than those from control individuals. (Ref. 164)' Song, Chan, and Sun (2020)

I am no longer sure that the term *processed foods* sufficiently alerts us to pay attention; when I examine labels I always seem to spot an additive that is not a supplement like added vitamins, I often spot stabilizers and preservatives. See C. A. Monteiro et al. (2019) and see this excerpt from their paper. *Monteiro et al also identify: '[u]ltra-processed foods already make up more than half of the total dietary energy [consumption in the high-income USA] [] and between one-fifth and one-third of total dietary energy in middle-income countries such as Brazil, Mexico, and Chile.'* This is disastrous because these foods have been and are being linked to several pressing health situations, including greater risks of obesity, colon cancer, and chronic disease situations, e.g., dementia and cardiovascular disease.

¹⁹ *Findings* by Chong et al. (2023) ... 'In 2019, age-standardized malnutrition-related disability-adjusted life years (DALYs) was 680 (95% UI: 507 - 895) per 100,000 population. DALY rates decreased from 2000 to 2019 (-2.86% annually), projected to fall 8.4% from 2020 to 2030. Africa and low Socio-Demographic Index (SDI) countries observed the highest malnutrition-related DALYs. Age-standardized obesity-related DALY estimates were 1933 (95% UI: 1277 - 2640). Obesity-related DALYs rose 0.48% annually from 2000 to 2019, predicted to increase by 39.8% from 2020 to 2030. The highest obesity-related DALYs were in Eastern Mediterranean and middle SDI countries. **Interpretation** The ever-increasing *obesity* burden, on the backdrop of curbing the *malnutrition* burden, is predicted to rise further.'

- Research is revealing that it is not just the low nutritional value²⁰ that is harming us but also #active agents in ultra-processed foods that impact our biological functioning. An Italian study by Bonaccio et al. (2022) found that #InflammatoryMarkers, e.g., a higher white blood cell count, were higher in groups that ate the most ultra-processed foods. It is well known that our bodies trigger an inflammatory response for invading cancer cells and pathogens (bacteria or viruses) signaling our Immune System (including said white blood cells, e.g., Naïve CD8 T-Cells) to attack the invaders. Mantovani and Garlanda (2023) Do ultra-processed foods contain #active agents that engage a response from our Immune System? Inflammation? The Conclusion in the Abstract of Bonaccio (B) et al ends with: ‘[] the relation between a high ultra-processed food intake and mortality was not explained by the poor quality of these foods.’ B et al show that increased ultra-processed food consumption is associated with higher cardiovascular and all-cause mortality and the authors state that: ‘Ultra-processed food intake ... remained associated with mortality even after the poor nutritional quality of the diet was accounted for.’ A danger that appears to be independent of the poor nutritional quality of the diet meaning we need further investigation to identify the root causes of the dangers presented by ultra-processed foods; what #active agents are in those foods? A USA-based study reporting on a very large prospective investigation showed that high consumption of “total ultra-processed foods in men and certain subgroups of ultra-processed foods in men and women was associated with an increased risk of colorectal cancer.” “These associations remained significant after further adjustment for body mass index or indicators of nutritional quality of the diet.” Wang et al. (2022) This is a presentation of a danger independent of the body mass index or indicators of nutritional quality of the diet, again prompting me to ask what #active agents are in those foods, the root causes of the dangers.

- The above text block is the outcome of a review of Bonaccio et al. (2022), Wang et al. (2022), C. Monteiro and Cannon (2022),
- The above text block raised this question for me are we

²⁰ The industrial processes producing the ultra-processed foods destroy the natural structure of the food ingredients and reduce or completely erode fiber, vitamins, minerals, and phytochemicals.

exposing ourselves to #active agents presenting a significant danger to us if we consume ultra-processed foods?

Using The EU Precautionary Principle

- Can these dangers be part of the messaging guiding people and populations toward plant-based diets? One of my hopes for this course is to assist us in becoming knowledgeable questioners/cross-examiners, e.g., with knowledge of the EU's Precautionary Principle call for preventive action. Commission (2000) Here I will argue that the EU Precautionary Principle can be inspirational for allowing us to position ourselves as knowledgeable questioners/cross-examiners addressing uncertain dangers.
 - Dietary interventions may also present opportunities to mitigate dangerous outcomes due to exposure to air pollutants. See Zhu et al. *“Interaction between plant-based dietary pattern and air pollution on cognitive function: a prospective cohort analysis of Chinese older adults.”* Lancet Regional Health - Western Pacific, vol. 20, 1 Mar. 2022, p. 100372 [https://www.thelancet.com/journals/lanwpc/article/PIIS2666-6065\(21\)00281-9/fulltext](https://www.thelancet.com/journals/lanwpc/article/PIIS2666-6065(21)00281-9/fulltext) **Interpretation published by authors:** “Plant-based dietary pattern may attenuate detrimental impacts of PM2.5 on cognitive function among older adults. Adherence to the plant-based dietary pattern could be used to prevent adverse neurological effects caused by air pollution, especially in developing regions.” I would be aware of this work but be cautious, so far no one is citing back to it, and the role of plant-based diets remains incompletely understood, it is undoubtedly a work in progress. Consider this, they do not have a Figure 2 of <http://bit.ly/Ornishetal2013>, see <https://www.evernote.com/1/AAfXvT7y0Q9CYK7XcMBJlkZYRlwS2Lejmws>. You might consider looking at it as an idea for a final paper suggestion and exploring the issues yourself. Final Papers are due _____.
 - For **Assginment_1d** please ask for your speculative writing, what messages are we sending out to the public

we are focusing on, I recommend including a message on precautionary action, e.g., shielding yourself from **Oxidative Stress (OS)** related to, e.g., Psychological Incursions, Air Pollution and **What is on the end of your Fork. Can the food we eat be a shield against OS?** I would use some imaginative reasoning and think about what is likely causal/causes. I am using this diagram, I am calling it a **framework** to promote reasoning,

Figure 3: U, X and Y

- The above Framework is here https://bit.ly/CausalTeachingNotes_UXY Updated_20230418
 - The URL for the pink text is https://bit.ly/PinkNotes_Causal,
 - And see Causal_TeachingNotes: A First Glance:

[https://www.evernote.com/l/AAd625eP1xBCT7Tw1IQcIZ_weDttUQzK3JY,](https://www.evernote.com/l/AAd625eP1xBCT7Tw1IQcIZ_weDttUQzK3JY)

- What are the various ways we can shield ourselves from **Oxidative Stress (OS)**? For some of your submissions on Assignment_1b, some of you referenced OS; we are building towards this flow,
 - ... Stress (E.g., Psychological Incursions, Air Pollution, **What is on the end of your Fork,**) ** »> **Oxidative Stress / Inflammation** »> DNA Damage »> Telomere Shortening »> More DNA Damage »> Mutations »> E.g., Immune System Fails (in some areas of its functions) hurtling us towards **A Compromised Immune System, leading to dangerous infections or E.g., Cancerous Cells Develop,**
 - ** Please spend a little time thinking of ways we can shield ourselves from Stress. What do we tell people? #SpeculativeWriting #IdeasLab
- The promotion of an **#IdeasLab** as a teaching strategy in this course is attempting to raise awareness of Environmental Health Science, Public Health, and the **EU Precautionary Principle**.^{21 22} One of the objectives is to assist the course members in becoming *knowledgeable questioners/cross examiners*, e.g., with knowledge of the **EU's Precautionary Principle** call for preventive action in the face of uncertain but suggestive evidence of danger. Commission (2000) We are placing the **EU Precautionary Principle** as a foundation for informing ourselves we are the analysts who can be the interpreters of Public Health anomalies. My teaching experience suggests that casting the members as analysts of *uncertain dangers* assists the flow of their narrative generation, increasing the possibilities of learning for and forming collectives focusing on **Prevention**.²³

²¹ I am arguing that the **EU Precautionary Principle** is inspirational for allowing members of the course to position themselves as *analysts* who can be the rescuers. Can these dangers be part of the messaging guiding people and populations towards, e.g., plant-based diets? One of our hopes for our teaching is to be an assistant on the journey to becoming knowledgeable questioners/cross examiners, e.g., with knowledge of the **EU's Precautionary Principle** call for preventive action in the face of uncertain but suggestive evidence of danger. Commission (2000) See this as a call for a cross examiner's approach, <https://bit.ly/PrecautionaryAssessment>. Martuzzi and Tickner (2004) We are placing the **EU Precautionary Principle** as a foundation for informing ourselves that we can bring skepticism to a situation. **I am arguing for the formation of Prevention collectives.**

²² The promotion of an **#IdeasLab** as a teaching strategy in this course is attempting to raise awareness of Environmental Health Science, Public Health and the **EU Precautionary Principle**.

²³ My teaching experience suggests that casting the members as analysts of *uncertain dangers* assists the flow of their narrative generation, increasing the possibilities for collaboration.

Work In Progress Conclusions, Upshot Reflections

- Dear Class Members, Thank you so much for your shared reflections in Perusall on a draft of this paper dated 14 Feb 2023. I would like you to consider sharing your reflections as Upshot statements,²⁴
- In this draft, I share one of my Upshot statements on ChatGPT as not being able to theorize, or generate a theory, here are my updates on this, dated the 3rd March 2023.²⁵
- The dilemmas created by people crediting human attributes to an AI tool like ChatGPT (C) appear to initiate because some people use words to describe to other people their internal states. I argue that is likely to be a short-changing act for some other peoples' internal states; I am thinking of situations where words and language do not suffice to embrace human minds and hearts. This is where I kind of trust that humans will always be out in front of AI. This quote is from Jean-Louis Lebris de Kerouac, appearing in his autobiographical novel '*On The Road*' ... "*The only people for me are the mad ones, the ones who are mad to live, mad to talk, mad to be saved, desirous of everything at the same time.*" **We are trying to develop Reasoning.**²⁶ I am pitching a *scientific imagination* as skeptical,²⁷ ²⁸ statistical thinking (Tong (2019)) and causal thinking using a totality of the circumstances: you (**position-ality**) have gathered on the exposures, outcomes, **localities, positionalities** and your notions of underlying mechanisms, biological mechanisms. Choices based on intuition, especially when the assessor/estimator/guesser cannot tell you why they chose x are to my best estimate not as yet within the realm of AI > (Large) Language Models (LMs)> ChatGPT (C). I don't interpret C as producing a work-product where x is a theory or a predicted outcome.
- The results - work-product from C - in our research, I interpret as a modeling of the distribution of collected past human outputs in designated contexts; the collection of searchable, text-based formats accessible to C appears to be vast. I am not dismissing C's work-product, I am arguing it will prove to be a very useful collaborator augmenting our analysis. I posit C is not theorizing, the theorizing: best

²⁴ Dear Class, I would like you to consider publishing some of your reflections that were shared in Perusall in this paper, please see this example kindly provided by your colleague XXXXXXXX XXXXXXXX. https://bit.ly/LandUse_PlantBasedDiet.

²⁵ Dear Class Members, I hope that in discussion with you, we can consider submitting this paper with the addition of some of your credited Perusall reflections to the journal ...

²⁶ Jack Kerouac (2011) *On the Road*. Penguin Books

²⁷ *Why Skeptical: What's going on?* I argue that Health Disparities are an emergency that needs our investigatory skills and remedy actions.

²⁸ Constructing a research methodology that supports approaching an analysis of Health Disparities is a work in progress, see <https://bit.ly/EnvironmentalJusticeMatters>. The open-source tools available to my teaching / research setting are a series of Jupyter notebooks hosted at '*Practical Deep Learning for Coders*' primary author Jeremy Howard and the *ICOS Carbon Portal Jupyter Hub*, these tools are a low-cost entry point for promoting research. With this strategy, one of the objectives is to create situations for the development of hypotheses of relevance to public health, environmental health and worthy of public sharing. The scope of this research design facilitates embracing Public Health Data both locally and globally. My research goals, include developing what I call an *#IdeasLab* learning space described in this past assignment, *Saving Lives, Speculative Design on #theCoincidence of #Asthma Hospitalizations and #COVID-19 Disease, Ongoing Reflections on Sars-CoV-2* <https://zenodo.org/record/4702004/files/handout-IntroCancerPrevention.pdf?download=1>.

estimates on outcomes is still a realm of humans and other life forms. Consider collaborating with C on future assignments: <http://bit.ly/SpeculativeWriting>. C will not be doing the best estimate on outcomes for you and me. Nor is C going to provide you with a prediction. It can give you a listing of the known, a collection of knowns that have been *recorded in a searchable text-based form*. It appears that C can curate the *recorded, searchable text-based forms* in response to our queries.

- *I recommend you use ChatGPT (and Google> Bard, my invite arrived 20230323,) with every assignment or project;* if you feel ChatGPT's work-product was valuable to your submission cite it as (ChatGPT, personal communication, March 3, 2023). I used GPT3.5 for the searches reported in this paper and not for the writing; GPT4.0 is now in the market; this YouTube review of both positions 4.0 as an improvement with more accurate outcomes, queries its opensource creds and highlights *multimodality*, meaning 4 was trained on both text and images. See <https://youtu.be/6Hewb1wIOlo> by @AnastasiInTech ... Mar 16, 2023: "In this video, I share my insights on GPT-4. I test GPT-4 and compare it to GPT-3.5. The paper [I used is] 'GPT-4 Technical Report.' <https://cdn.openai.com/papers/gpt-4.pdf>"
- *Dear Class Members,* I would like to add some of your Perusall commentaries on this document to this document; for example see Supplement 1., initiated by your colleague XXXXXXXX XXXXXXXX, who kindly provided permission to use her excellent initiating statement:. **XXXXXXX wrote in our Perusall shared forum: 'I don't think everyone going on plant-based diets will help with economy or crisis around the world.'**
(XXXXXXX XXXXXXXX: is a member of the Spring 2023 Course, Prevention Research, <https://stjohns.digication.com/kmoses/home>)

Best to you,

KM

K Moses JD PhD

K.Moses@Outlook.com

Supplement 1.

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Introduction

In our Perusall²⁹ shared learning space we reviewed: *'ChatGPT and Imaginative Reasoning in the Classroom Space: What would be your design for a campaign to persuade people to adopt a plant-based diet?'*,³⁰ in one of many responses our colleague XXXXXXX commented, wrote:

"I don't think everyone going on plant-based diets will help with economy or crisis around the world."

For XXXXXXX's Perusall commentary see Supplement 1.1. at <https://www.evernote.com/shard/s7/sh/8acf061d-ef2a-468a-a88b-053eece58dfa/cc668e424f17694ec9aaa997ee76ca69>, <- not yet open, awaiting permissions,

(XXXXXXXX XXXXXXX: a member of the Spring 2023 Course, Prevention Research, <https://stjohns.digication.com/kmoses/home>)

XXXXXXXX, thank you for persuading me (KM) to explore your statement, as you can see from the data shared below the argument for a Plant-Based Diet irrespective of health benefits and reduction of global warming is economically sound.

Eating meat is the end stage(s) of the chain: (1) Growing plant-based Livestock feeds,³¹ (2) Land devoted to pasture for Livestock, (3) Feeding and Slaughtering Livestock,³² (4) Packaging and Sale of the bits cut from the Livestock, (5) ... The Bits are eaten by Humans,

My best estimate is that (1) and (2) are economically big and significant in the human food chain.

The Question I used in ChatGPT is

How much land is used for animal feed globally?

²⁹ <https://www.perusall.com/>

³⁰ Moses, Kevin. 'Designing> Assignment_1d> ChatGPT and Imaginative Reasoning in the Classroom Space: What would be your design for a campaign to persuade people to adopt a plant-based diet?' 9 Feb. 2023. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7632542> The latest version is always here, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7626711>

³¹ It is a very harsh industry: the UK where I was born has a history of feeding Sheep Intestines, Offal to Cattle; they got it so wrong, ushering into the human population eating the Cattle, a Prion -> Mad Cow Disease in Cattle, deadly Brain Injuries in Humans. CDC (2021)

³² What of those slaughterhouses, who gets to work there? Dreier (2023) 'Alone and Exploited, Migrant Children Work Brutal Jobs Across the U.S.' <https://nyti.ms/3IPNjd9>

Results:

- The amount of land used for animal feed globally varies depending on the type of animal feed and the source of information. However, according to a study published in the journal "Nature" in 2018, approximately 83% of the world's agricultural land is used for livestock production, either to grow feed crops or to provide pasture for grazing animals. This includes land used for grazing, as well as land used to grow crops such as corn, soybeans, and alfalfa that are used for animal feed.
- Another study published in the journal "Global Environmental Change" in 2020 estimated that around 77% of global agricultural land is dedicated to feeding livestock. This study used a more comprehensive approach, including both feed crops and grazing land, and also took into account indirect land use changes associated with feed production.
- It's worth noting that these estimates are subject to some degree of uncertainty and may vary depending on the data sources and methods used to make the calculations.

I chose: REGENERATE

- It is difficult to provide an exact figure for how much land is used for animal feed globally as it can vary depending on various factors such as the type of animals being raised, the location, and the production methods used. However, it is estimated that approximately 33% of the world's arable land is used for growing animal feed.
- According to a report by the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) of the United Nations, around 80% of the world's soybean crop is used for animal feed, with the rest being used for human consumption, biofuels, and other purposes. Corn is another major animal feed crop, with around 40% of the world's corn production

being used for animal feed. Other crops commonly used for animal feed include wheat, barley, and sorghum.

- In addition to cropland, animal feed production can also impact other types of land such as forests and grasslands that are converted into pasture or used for growing feed crops. This can have significant environmental impacts such as deforestation, loss of biodiversity, and soil degradation.

I decided to do a Google comparison, I(KM) do not find the above that good, and I want something I can cite on the numbers. First, I Just Googled It -> 'How much land is used for animal feed globally?' with quotation marks.

See my result below, ... I did not go to Google Scholar but it is an option, Google did not like my construction but I am OK with it removing my quotation marks, check out the below,

I like the look of the third hit,

OurWorldinData. *'Half of the World's Habitable Land Is Used for Agriculture'*. Our World in Data, 4 Mar. 2023, <https://ourworldindata.org/global-land-for-agriculture>. I turned the web page into a PDF and captured this image from the web page:

I (KM) regard the three lower tiers as fabulously informative: the land distribution (37 million KM²) to support Livestock is 3.4-fold higher than Crops (11 million KM²) and deliver only 18% of our calorie supply whereas Crops deliver 82%. WTH ... The global economy/population needs to end the Livestock game. I don't eat meat but if you do, check out the dynamics.

Reminder XXXXXXX wrote: **I don't think everyone going on plant-based diets will help with the economy or crisis around the world.**

The data shared here indicates the cost distribution to Livestock/Animal Feed is significant and the resulting calorie value is low compared to a Plant-Based Diet Food Chain. Irrespective of health benefits and reduction of global warming Plant-Based Diets are economically sound.

Figure 4: Land and Animal Feed

Global land use for food production

Figure 5: Land Use

LET'S ALSO THINK ABOUT THE FUTURE OF AI> (LARGE) LANGUAGE MODELS> E.g., OpenAI> ChatGPT and Google> Bard

Google's AI> Language Model is called 'Bard' and is arriving any-time now,

Google Brain is the powerhouse of their AI; Google products using it are

- Recommendations provided by YouTube
- Search functionality for Google Photos
- Android's Speech Recognition
- Google Translate
- Smart Reply on Gmail

I also think AI (Artificial Intelligence) is quite a bit of a stretch, a misnomer, ChatGPT is a Language Model: I have only explored text searches. I think I am getting back a curation of the known searchable texts, a sub-collection of knowns that have been recorded in a searchable text-based form. The collection of the knowns searched is vast; the generation of the retrieved sub-collection has limitations

based on the format: a searchable text-based form. It appears that ChatGPT can curate a response gleaned from recorded, searchable text-based forms. I have to research the 'curate' methodology, I think I am getting back pre-existing sentences and no sentences made de novo, the latter would be the intelligence step. Dear Class, I highly recommend you explore querying ChatGPT and 'Bard' as soon as it is open to you. I am also recommending you give some thought to what might be the YouTube recommendation algorithm(s), and how it works. It's the best I have seen. My number 2 is Google Photos. Some of you are telling me, and each other, TikTok is better.

My thanks to you all,

Best wishes,

K Moses JD PhD

MosesK@StJohns.edu

<https://stjohns.digication.com/kmoses/home>

If you are sharing content for the courses via Google Docs, I am at Docs.Moses@gmail.com and GoogleVoice +13473526626,

I am available for office hours via Microsoft Teams at

<https://bit.ly/OfficeHoursWithKMoses>

... please alert me with an email if you need a specific time in the below window:

- Optional for you, all of you: Mon - Thurs 1230 to 1330 NYC - you are also welcome to use these time slots for any course content you want to be covered,

If you want to veer way off this reference point for office hours, email me and I will make adjustments for your time zone,

Supplement 2. Google search is pretty good, it has access to the EUA from the FDA,

https://www.google.com/search?q=baricitinib&rlz=1C5CHFA_enUS570US570&oq=baricitinib&aqs=chrome..69i57j35i39j0i67i650l2j0i512j0i67i650l4j0i512.4146j0j7&sourceid=chrome&ie=UTF-8#ip=1

Baricitinib EUA Fact Sheet

Food and Drug Administration (.gov) <https://www.fda.gov/media/download>

“This EUA is for the unapproved use of baricitinib to treat COVID-19 in hospitalized pediatric patients 2 to less than 18 years of age requiring supplemental ...”

Consider trying the variations in the Google Search: “FDA” AND “criteria” AND “baricitinib”

Please see the next page for my continuing use of Google Bard,

Figure 6: Supplement 2. In a test run with Google> Bard, I asked for a return on the word 'baricitinib', 202303231502UTC. See the update in Supplement 3.

Supplement 3. Updating my usage of Bard, 20230523231555UTC

It is 20230521231555UTC, and the Semester is nearing its end, here are my reflections on using AI this Spring 2023 Semester, shared via CANVAS> Announcements> Note_XX

I updated Supplement 3, created a separate note, and hosted it here <https://bit.ly/TheAIregister> 20230716185508UTC

- In the *Spring 2023 Semester*, I promoted the use of AI to the members of a Prevention Research Course with, e.g., Moses, K. *'Designing> Assignment_1d> Large Language Models and Imaginative Reasoning in the Classroom Space.'* 9 Feb. 2023, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7626711> > the latest PDF was uploaded 20230717 https://zenodo.org/record/8155031/files/ChatGPTReasoning_20230717123201_.pdf?download=1. In this example, I provided use cases of AI with the assignment question. I suspect a number of the students were already into AI. My current interpretation after a teaching semester collaborating with AI as a research assistant is that it can bring us all forward. The proposal of AI as a research assistant comes from directly presenting assignment questions to AI, presenting subdivisions of the questions to AI, and promoting the course members to do the same. See <https://bit.ly/PreventionResearchAI>. An outcome for me is to urge course members to use AI to assist with story discovery and analysis and credit the AI work-product.
- I suspect the challenges will include filtering and fact-checking the AI work-product despite my treating the source material AI is trained on as accurate. My default position is to trust the source material until proof suggesting the source is inaccurate is revealed because thinking otherwise is being drawn into a dangerous conspiracy pit of distrust that is not the skepticism I advocate for in my teaching practice. The skepticism I promote explores AI-delivered facts and curating. A very good practice for our classroom collaboration is a cross-examination of the curating, the stringing it all together into deliverables. The use cases I brought to the course members, in Spring 2023,

Figure 7: Crediting the work-product of AI,

did not lead me to interpret AI as a *teacher*. I am asking the course members the same question: *is it a teacher?* I trust AI as a research assistant to which I bring my critical thinking. We likely think of critical thinkers as being '*smart and do[ing] things that intelligent and observant people would do[.]*' by Jordan Peele, speaking of the filmgoers for his film "*Get Out*" 2017, <https://perma.cc/T246-AG6R>. The core logic in science is testing our theories with new evidence, the very thing Mr Peele is speaking of. I argue that this is the scientific method. I am still questioning AI on this. **Prompt> Here is a dose-response data set, please compile an X Y plot using the data set at this location on my computer, the computer we are currently on ...**

- It appears to me that AI is stringing together words/word chunks with no way to check if what is strung together is accurately strung together. Curating gathered information fragments and delivering the montage is limited by programming parameters, including the visions of the programmer. (Ref. Lee, Resnick, and Barton (2019), Bolukbasi et al. (2016)) I assure you the programmer is not Walter Benjamin. (Buck-Morss (1989)) My best estimate is the same old sequential decision tree is operating; "the because" includes examining the marketing: the said tree is not lauded as novel. The decision tree is faster via more efficient programming languages and hardware but that does not go to the veracity of the curation. The source material is treated and promoted as accurate by me(KM) until we find falsification evidence. Writing in the style of the sources does not mean that the curation will be accurate and trustworthy. *Critical thinking and skepticism* when working with AI as a research assistant are vital. This can help us ensure that we are using our judgment and gathered information (Many Sources of Data (MSOD)) to verify the accuracy and relevance of the information/curation provided. Tong (2019) Our course, *Prevention Research*, is going for the best estimate(s) on exposures and outcomes of interest to us; I also raised this example: Moses, K. '*Saving Lives, Speculative Writing on #theCoIncidence of #Asthma Hospitalizations and #COVID-19 Disease, ... Ongoing Reflections on Sars-CoV-2, A Compromised Immune System and Risk Assessment.*'

11 Oct. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4107131>
> Look For the Latest Draft > 28th April 2023, 3.3MB:
https://zenodo.org/record/7876326/files/handout-IntroPreventionResearch_SpeculativeWriting_202304281634UTC.pdf?download=1 ... Give it a try with AI as the collaborating research assistant, check if the AI can get to the best estimate on the *why question*. I am ending the Semester with a recommendation to use both:

- *OpenAI* via <https://github.com/Significant-Gravitas/Auto-GPT>, I reached a use Limit for ChatGPT, error message: 'API Rate Limit Reached' I had to switch to a paid account, I interpret this as a loss for the Education space and using ChatGPT as a research assistant,
- The *Google entry*> *Bard* via "bard-rs 1.0.6 - Docs.rs." <https://docs.rs/crate/bard-rs/1.0.6>. ... I interpreted this as a beautiful rendering of AI. Built with *Rust*, I am a fan of the programming language *Rust*. It is fast, making *Rust* a good choice for high-performance applications,
 - * Designing for the future: *bard-rs* comes with a setup that allows users to save the chat history with Bard as a Markdown file in realtime, an 'internal register'.³³

My research practice includes both a commitment to maintaining an *internal register* for my research with *Bard* and a disclosed *register* for the shared learning space where I + the class members publish the *Bard/AI response* to our assignments, questions, and problems we are tackling.

- The *register* for the shared classroom/learning space where I + the class members publish the *Bard/AI response* to our assignments and questions is published at https://bit.ly/AIregister_PreventionResearch.³⁴ I promoted AI as another player for this space. Our conversations with AI will be memorialized at this *register*. Hopefully, some of the AI work-products will be contributors to story discovery and the development of our analysis.

³³ I did a review of record keeping, most liking the appearance of the term *internal register* for conveying the role of record keeping and the guidance provided here: 'Record-Keeping | Responsible Research.' 16 July 2023, <https://www.responsible-research.ubc.ca/evolving-topics-responsible-research/record-keeping>. I am recommending this page's: DID YOU KNOW? (1) A complete and accurate research record goes beyond clearly documenting where we obtained the research materials; why, when, and how we generate, collect, or analyze data; and what our observations, interpretations, and next steps are. ...

³⁴ The Class members during the Spring 2023 Semester used a variety of AI platforms. A favourite appears to be the writing platform Jarvis AI / Jasper AI.

- Why a *register*: it is obvious that AI is a player in our learning space.³⁵ I have proposed we make AI a go-to research collaborator by pitching its take into our conversations and crediting what we use. We will publish the AI work-products on the problems we tackle to the under-construction https://bit.ly/AIregister_PreventionResearch. *My proposal is the AI register becomes a presence in the learning space and we update it with the AI work-product on the problems we are tackling during the Semester.* Moses (2023)
- The first Assignment in the Fall 2023 *Prevention Research* course is https://bit.ly/Assignment_1_. *I am publishing the Bard work-product on this Assignment to the AI register page.* 20230711205348UTC

³⁵ In April 2023 some class member submissions reached a distinct uptick for the insertion of AI-generated texts.

A micro-debate with class members in Spring 2023 was on AI as a curator of existing info., not a creator, some members agreed, and some disagreed. The split was 50:50. A few thought the description aggregator was better than curator, which they felt bestowed an agency that was not there,

- An outcome for me was the decision to create an *AI register*; I do not know the outcomes for the student members, but I do know via my subjective sampling that members were equally distributed across used and credited usage of the AI work-product, used without crediting usage, and some did not use. *I requested crediting for any usage of AI work-products.*
- I checked usage by asking Bard if a text example was created by AI. This is a *Fool's Errand*, going-forward I will not check student work with an AI review. I will request and provide examples of crediting work and will explore the development of AI.³⁶

³⁶ The large language models (LLMs) will be constantly updated with more parameters and better text generation; detection of AI work-products is likely wasting my/your time.

I(KM) try to run our learning space as an #IdeasLab; the Assignments ask for a speculative writing response and predictions on Public Health issues and futures.

- I started a Bard conversation on the creator issue. See Figure 1, page 3. Bard's response suggests that the AI future in the

classroom space is a must-be-included research collaborator.

```
You: Bard you have written that: The word "generative" in this context means "creating something new." ... Is this accurate, I see Bard as a curator or not a creator of the new and novel, I am using "novel" according to US Patent Law. Is my interpretation accurate?
Bard: I see what you mean.

I would say that I am both a curator and a creator. I am a curator in the sense that I am able to access and process a vast amount of information, and I am able to select and present information in a way that is relevant and useful to the user. However, I am also a creator in the sense that I am able to generate new content, such as text, images, and music.

Whether or not my creations are novel under US Patent Law is a matter of interpretation. I am not a lawyer, so I cannot provide legal advice. However, I can say that my creations are often original and creative, and they are not simply copies of existing works.

Ultimately, whether or not my creations are patentable is up to the USPTO to decide.

I hope this helps!

You: █
session-moses > moses > < | Bard-rs bard-rs | Moses Moses | 10:24 01 Jun 23
```

Figure 8: Crediting the work-product of AI, 20230601

- I suggested that we follow the progress of AI development by distinguishing its curating of text-based sources and asking AI to speculate on and predict outcomes for the Public Health issues we are addressing in our learning space. My current understanding is that AI cannot predict nor speculatively write. To distinguish our work from the AI work-products I will promote speculative writing on solutions to the problems we are tackling. One of the objectives for an #IdeasLab approach is *Futurism*: speculatively writing on healing the harms at the root causes of Health Disparities.
- My work with Bard as of 20230919 has reached the stage of editing Prompts for particular tasks, my current finest is: **Identify any gaps in the following block of text, I am naming the block of text 'AIcheck_1to_2'. Please do the identification of gaps, step by step. 'AIcheck_1to_2' is written including Quarto syntax; if you have suggestions, please share. AIcheck_1to_2: ...**

Analyses are conducted with R version 4.2.2 with the `hmisc` (5.1.1), `rUM` (1.0.2), `table1` (1.4.3) packages used to preprocess and summarize data. (R Core Team 2022; Harrell 2023; Balise et al. 2023; Rich 2023)

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